

β-Diketones in Ring Formation, Part IV.

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Ascertaining certain factors which govern the course of reaction between a substance containing a reactive methylene group, such as cyanoacetamide, and an αγ-dicarbonyl compound (Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 481, 815), it was now found necessary to have also an idea of the influence of a negative substituent, CO₂Et, CO·R etc., at the methylene carbon atom of the dicarbonyl compound on the course of this reaction.

Accordingly ethyl diacetoacetate (I) was treated with cyanoacetamide in dilute alcoholic solution in presence of a little piperidine when no condensation product separated after 3 or 4 days. On acidifying the solution however even after a day, a product was isolated which unlike the pyridone derivative previously synthesised (Basu, *loc. cit.*), easily dissolved in sodium carbonate solution with effervescence and gave a characteristic coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. It had the formula C₇H₆O₂N₂ and was identified as 2-keto-3-cyano-4-methyl-6-hydroxy-1:2-dihydropyridine (II) by its hydrolysis to the known 4-methyl-2:6-dihydropyridine (III) (Rogerson and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 1688) and by its synthesis from cyanoacetamide and ethyl acetoacetate (*cf.* Guareschi, *R. Accad. Sci. Torino., Chem. Zentr.*, 1896, 1, 602; 1896, II, 46). It becomes evident that during condensation one of the acetyl groups of ethyl diacetoacetate was eliminated as was also perceived from a distinct smell of ethyl acetate in the reaction mixture. This occurred even when the reaction was conducted at 0° or with cyanoacetmethylamide when *N*-methyl derivative of 2-keto-3-cyano-4-methyl-6-hydroxy-1:2-dihydropyridine (II) was easily isolated.

The question now arises whether in the reaction with such dicarbonyl compounds, ethyl diacetoacetate, ethyl acetoacetate (β-ketonic

esters), the ethylenic linkage formed by the enolisation of the keto-group is responsible for the initial condensation or the carbonyl group remaining as such, becomes the centre of reaction. Thorpe and Rogerson (*loc. cit.*), and Thorpe (*Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, p. 51) are of opinion that ethyl cyanoacetate preferentially reacts with the enolic form of ethyl acetoacetate to give rise to a glutaconic ester derivative. Similarly cyanoacetamide might have reacted with the enolic form of acetoacetic ester or diacetoacetic ester to give rise to the same (by the elimination of an acetyl group in the latter case) pyridone derivative.

So ethyl ethoxycrotonate (IV), an *O*-ether of ethyl acetoacetate in which the ethylenic bond is fixed, was prepared and its reaction with cyanoacetamide studied, when 2-keto-3-cyano-4-methyl-6-hydroxy-1:2-dihydropyridine (II), m.p. 304° (decomp.) was easily isolated. The formation of this may now be represented in the following way:—

Similarly ethyl β -aminocrotonate (X) when heated with cyanoacetamide afforded 2-keto-3-cyano-4-methyl-6-hydroxy-1:2-dihydropyridine.

Next a cyclic β -ketonic ester, ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (V) was condensed with cyanoacetamide to synthesise 3-keto-4-cyano-1-hydroxy-2:3:5:6:7:8-hexahydroisoquinoline (VI) which on hydrolysis with hydrochloric acid gave 1:3-dihydroxy-5:6:7:8-tetrahydroisoquinoline (VII). The isoquinoline derivative (VI) was also obtained when ethyl tetrahydroanthranilate (VIII) was heated with cyanoacetamide under the experimental conditions described later. The tetrahydroanthranilate did not undergo any appreciable decomposition when heated alone under the same experimental conditions and afforded no condensation product when treated with benzal benzoylacetone, $\text{Ph} \cdot \text{CH} = \text{C}(\text{CO} \cdot \text{CH}_3) \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{Ph}$. A similar mixture of the latter and ethyl β -aminocrotonate gives a crystalline product (IX) as found by Knoevenagel (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 2188). The inactivity of

the ethyl tetrahydroanthranilate shows that the presence of a labile methine hydrogen atom* as present in the β-aminocrotonic ester (X) is essential for the above reaction or in other words the β-ketonic ester derivatives react in the form (VIII) or (X) in the condensation reaction (cf. also Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1892, 61, 835). This again points to the preferential addition of the methylene group to the ethylenic linkage present in systems as represented above, in this type of reaction.

The compounds described in this paper react in accordance with the formula (XI) and thereby it is in agreement with that of the pyridone derivative (XII) obtained by condensing a β-diketone with cyanoacetamide (Basu, *loc. cit.*), the only difference being that the former (XI) contains a hydroxyl group, the presence of which increases the acidity of these compounds even in the *N*-methyl derivatives whereas the corresponding derivatives of (XII) are not soluble even in caustic alkali. The above condensation products have thus been described as ketohydroxy derivatives.

In Part III of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 119) it has been shown that *p*-toluoylacetoneamine $\text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{CH}^* = \text{C}(\text{CH}_3) \cdot \text{NH}_2$ when heated with cyanoacetamine gave 3-cyano-4-methyl-6-*p*-tolyl-2-pyridone identical with that obtained from *p*-toluoylacetone itself. Here it has been found that benzoylacetone amine $\text{Ph} \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{CH}^* = \text{C}(\text{CH}_3) \cdot \text{NH}_2$ (Fischer and Bülow, *Ber.*, 1885, 18, 2134 ; Claisen, *Ber.*, 1926, 59, 144) similarly afforded 3-cyano-4-methyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone, m. p. 310°, (Basu, *loc. cit.*). This on methylation gave 3-cyano-1:4-dimethyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone, m. p. 265°, which on hydrolysis with concentrated hydrochloric acid was converted into 1:4-dimethyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone isolated in the form of its hydrochloride, the free base being an oil soluble in ether but giving no sharp coloration to alcoholic ferric chloride. Benzoylacetoneamine has also been found to react with benzalbenzoylacetone by Knoevenagel (*loc. cit.*). But from a similar experiment with an amine, $\text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{C}(\text{Me}) = \text{C}(\text{Me}) \cdot \text{NH}_2$ prepared from methylacetylacetone where there is no methine hydrogen atom, no definite condensation product was isolated, whereas *p*-toluoylacetoneamine gave, when heated with benzalbenzoylacetone, 2-methyl-4:6-diphenyl-3-*p*-toluoyl-5-acetyl-1:4-dihydropyridine (XIII), m. p. 183°, as a yellow crystalline solid. Further work with dicarbonyl compounds containing the substituent at the methylene carbon atom is in progress.

(XI)

(XII)

(XIV)

(XIII)

(XV)

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl Diacetoacetate and Cyanoacetamide: Formation of 2-Keto-3-cyano-4-methyl-6-hydroxy-1:2-dihydropyridine.—The ester was prepared according to Claisen and Zedel (*Annalen*, 1893, 277, 175) and obtained as a colourless liquid, b. p. 82°/6 mm. The copper salt melted at 150-51°. Cyanoacetamide (4.2 g.) was dissolved in water by warming and the ester (8.6 g.) added, with just enough alcohol to effect the solution. The solution was then warmed at about 50° with the addition of piperidine (2 c.c.) but no crystal separated out even after 6 hours. Smell of ethyl acetate was distinctly perceived in the reaction mixture when a further quantity of piperidine (1 c.c.) being added it was left overnight. The clear solution on acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid gave a crystalline solid (3.6 g.). On crystallisation from boiling water it melted at 304° with decomposition sintering earlier. (Found: C, 55.57; H, 4.31; N, 18.45. $C_7H_6O_2N_2$ requires C, 56.0; H, 4.0; N, 18.67 per cent.).

The compound is soluble in boiling water, alcohol and acetic acid. It dissolves in alkali and in alkaline carbonate with effervescence and gives with alcoholic ferric chloride a deep bluish-violet and with sodium nitrite solution a bluish-green coloration. The substance was heated with the concentrated acid at 150-60° for about 4 hours in a sealed tube and the acid product was made alkaline with ammonia and slowly neutralised with acetic acid when crystals that separated were collected and on crystallisation from dilute alcohol melted at 194°. (Found: N, 10.96. $C_6H_7O_2N$ requires N, 11.2 per cent.). It also dissolves in sodium carbonate solution with effervescence, gives with sodium nitrite solution a blue coloration and with alcoholic ferric chloride a reddish-violet coloration disappearing on warming, and possesses all the characteristics ascribed to 4-methyl-2:6-dihydropyridine (III) by Rogerson and Thorpe (*loc. cit.*). The mother compound was then found to be 2-keto-3-cyano-4-methyl-6-hydroxy-1:2-dihydropyridine (II) and as further proved by its synthesis from ethyl acetoacetate and cyanoacetamide (*vide infra*).

Ethyl Diacetoacetate and Cyanoacetmethylamide: Formation of 2-Keto-3-cyano-1:4-dimethyl-6-hydroxy-1:2-dihydropyridine (II, $NH=NCH_3$).—The condensation was effected as usual by means of piperidine and the product isolated after 2 days on acidification, crystallised from boiling water in clusters of needles, m.p. 274°.

(Found: N, 17.01. $C_8H_8O_2N_2$ requires N, 17.07 per cent.). It dissolves in sodium carbonate solution with effervescence, gives with sodium nitrite solution a green coloration and with ferric chloride a bluish-violet coloration which disappears on slight warming.

Condensation of Cyanoacetamide with Ethyl Acetoacetate and its Derivatives.

(i) The condensation between cyanoacetamide and ethyl acetoacetate was brought about in the usual way. The yield was only 35-40 per cent. On crystallisation from boiling water the product melted at 304° (decomp). The compound, 2-keto-3-cyano-4-methyl-6-hydroxy-1:2-dihydropyridine, has been already studied by Guareschi (*loc. cit.*).

(ii) *With Ethyl Ethoxycrotonate (IV).*—The *O*-ether of acetoacetic ester was prepared according to Claisen's method (*Ber.*, 1893, 26, 2731) and its condensation with sodiocyanoacetamide was effected exactly in the same way as in the case of other ethers similarly studied (Basu, *loc. cit.*). After 3 days water was added to have a clear solution. It was then extracted with ether. The ethereal solution on evaporation gave the unreacted ethyl ethoxycrotonate in its pure form in more than half the quantity used in the condensation. The aqueous solution on acidification afforded 2-keto-3-cyano-4-methyl-6-hydroxy-1:2-dihydropyridine (yield about 35 per cent.). On crystallisation from boiling water it melted at 304° (decomp). (Found: N, 18.52. $C_7H_6O_2N_2$ requires N, 18.67 per cent.). The condensation might also be brought about in presence of piperidine.

(iii) *With Ethyl β -Aminocrotonate.*—Molecular quantities of cyanoacetamide and ethyl β -aminocrotonate were heated at 130° on an oil-bath for about 15 minutes, when the usual condensation product was isolated in the form of its ammonium salt from which dilute hydrochloric acid liberated the free pyridine derivative melting at the same temperature when mixed with the product just described above.

Ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate and Cyanoacetamide: Formation of 3-Keto-4-cyano-1-hydroxy-2:3:5:6:7:8-hexahydroisoquinoline (VI).—The ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate was prepared from cyclohexanone and ethyl oxalate according to Kötze and Michael's method (*Annalen*, 1906, 350, 210) and obtained as a colourless liquid, b.p. $104-107^\circ/10$ mm. The yield was about 65 per cent. of the weight of cyclohexanone used. The condensation was effected both by

Knoevenagel's as well as by Michael's reaction. The former was conducted under the usual conditions and the latter as follows. To an alcoholic suspension of sodiocyanoacetamide prepared from an alcoholic solution of cyanoacetamide (8.4 g.) and sodium (2.3 g.) dissolved in absolute alcohol, an alcoholic solution of ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (17.0 g.) was gradually added with shaking. Soon the sodium salt dissolved and within a few minutes the contents of the flask changed into a thick sludge. It was left overnight. After 24 hours water was added and acidifying the clear solution a crystalline precipitate was obtained. The yield was about 85 per cent. On crystallisation from water or acetic acid it melted at 278° (decomp). (Found : N, 14.89, 14.92. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2$ requires N, 14.74 per cent.). The compound is soluble in boiling alcohol, alkali and in alkaline carbonate with effervescence. It imparts a deep bluish-violet coloration to alcoholic ferric chloride, but gives no colour reaction with sodium nitrite solution. On adding a concentrated solution of caustic potash, a potassium salt of the compound separated out. This crystallises from boiling water in small needles. (Found: K, 15.81. $C_{10}H_9O_2N_2K, H_2O$ requires K, 15.85 per cent.).

Hydrolysis: Formation of 1:3-Dihydroxy-5:6:7:8-tetrahydroisoquinoline.—The cyanoisoquinoline derivative (2 g.) was heated with fuming hydrochloric acid (20 c.c.) at 180° for about 5 hours. The reacted mixture on partial neutralisation with sodium carbonate gave a product which on crystallisation from alcohol (charcoal) melted at 205°. (Found: N, 8.65. $C_9H_{11}O_2N$ requires N, 8.48 per cent.). It is soluble in boiling water and in most organic solvents. It gives with sodium nitrite a bluish-green coloration on boiling. Ferric chloride gives a red coloration but it soon vanishes away. The dihydroxy compound dissolves in alkali and sodium carbonate solution with effervescence and forms a hydrochloride with concentrated hydrochloric acid, too soluble in water. It also reduces an ammoniacal solution of silver nitrate on boiling.

Methyl Derivative: 3-Keto-4-cyano-1-hydroxy-2-methyl-2:3:5:6:7:8-hexahydroisoquinoline (VI, NH=NMe).—Ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate was treated with sodiocyanoacetmethylamide in the same way as in the previous case. After 3 days the reacted mixture was concentrated on the water-bath and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The solid which separated, on crystallisation from boiling water was obtained in small prismatic needles with a mole-

cule of water of crystallisation, m.p. 199°. (Found: N, 12.52; H₂O, 7.84. C₁₁H₁₂O₂N₂, H₂O requires N, 12.61; H₂O, 8.10 per cent.). The anhydrous *iso*-quinoline derivative obtained by heating the substance in an air-bath at 110° melted at 202-203°. (Found: N, 13.56. C₁₁H₁₂O₂N₂ requires N, 13.73 per cent.). The compound is easily soluble in alcohol, difficultly in chloroform and ether and almost insoluble in benzene. It dissolves in sodium carbonate solution with effervescence, forms a silver salt, reduces a hot ammoniacal solution of silver nitrate and with ferric chloride solution gives a green coloration but it is very fugitive.

Ethyl Tetrahydroanthranilate and Cyanoacetamide.—The anthranilate derivative (VIII) was prepared by passing ammonia to ethyl *cyclohexanone*-2-carboxylate (Dieckmann, *Annalen*, 1901, 317, 27) and was heated with a molecular quantity of cyanoacetamide in an oil-bath at 120° for about 25 minutes. The solid found on crystallisation from dilute alcohol containing a trace of ammonia was obtained in clusters of needles, m.p. 320° with decomposition sintering and moistening earlier. (Found: N, 20.32. C₁₀H₉O₂N₂·NH₄ requires N, 20.29 per cent.) This is the ammonium salt of 3-keto-4-cyano-1-hydroxy-2:3:5:6:7:8-hexahydro*iso*quinoline. It is easily soluble in water and when its aqueous solution is treated with hydrochloric acid, the free compound, was isolated and melted at 278° with decomposition, not depressed when admixed with the *iso*quinoline derivative obtained from ethyl *cyclohexanone*-2-carboxylate. The compound itself or its hydrolysis product gradually becomes coloured.

The tetrahydroanthranilate when heated with benzalbenzoylacetone in alcoholic solution at 50° for about 5 days afforded no condensation product. On the contrary, smell of benzaldehyde and ethyl *cyclohexanone*carboxylate was distinctly perceived and the reaction mixture was completely soluble in ether (*cf.* Knoevenagel, *loc. cit.*).

Ethyl 5-Methyl-cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate and Cyanoacetamide: Formation of 3-Keto-4-cyano-6-methyl-1-hydroxy-2:3:5:6:7:8-hexahydroisoquinoline (XIV).—The β-ketonic ester was prepared from *m*-methyl*cyclohexanone* which yields more than 60% of its weight of ethyl 5 methyl*cyclohexanone*-2-carboxylate as a colourless oil boiling at 137-140°/25 mm. The condensation was effected with sodiocyanoacetamide in the usual way. The yield is almost theoretical. The compound crystallises from dilute alcohol in small

rectangular prisms, m.p. 271-72° (decomp). It slowly takes a pink tinge by coming in contact with air. (Found: N, 13.51. $C_{11}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 13.73 per cent.). It is soluble in sodium carbonate solution, gives with ferric chloride a deep bluish-violet coloration but no coloration with sodium nitrite.

Hydrolysis: Formation of 6-Methyl 1:3-dihydroxy-5:6:7:8-tetrahydroisoquinoline (XV).—The above compound on heating with hydrochloric acid in the usual way afforded a solid which after crystallisation from dilute alcohol melted at 200°. (Found: N, 8.15. $C_{10}H_{13}O_2N$ requires N, 7.82 per cent.). With sodium nitrite solution it gives no sharp coloration and with ferric chloride gives a light pink colour which soon disappears, but is easily soluble in alkali and alkaline carbonate solutions.

Benzoylacetoneamine and Cyanoacetamide: Formation of 3-Cyano-4-methyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone.—Benzoylacetoneamine (Knoevenagel, *Ber.* 1903, 36, 2187) and cyanoacetamide in molecular proportions when heated at 150° for about half an hour gave rise to a crystalline product with evolution of ammonia. This crystallises from glacial acetic acid in shining plates with a faint violet reflex, m.p. 310°. (Found: N, 13.35. $C_{13}H_{10}ON_2$ requires N, 13.33 per cent.). It was found to melt at the same temperature when mixed with an authentic sample of 3-cyano-4-methyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone (Basu, *loc. cit.*). Treating its sodium salt with methyl iodide in methyl alcoholic solution 3-cyano-1:4-dimethyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone was obtained. This crystallises from alcohol in long prismatic needles with a violet reflex, m.p. 265° (*cf.* Bardhan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, p. 2228). (Found: N, 12.63. $C_{14}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 12.5 per cent.). The compound is insoluble in caustic alkali. On hydrolysis with hydrochloric acid in the usual way an oil was isolated on neutralising the acid solution. The oil was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was dried and dry hydrogen chloride was passed into it when crystal began to separate and this on recrystallisation from dilute hydrochloric acid melted at 163°, sintering earlier. (Found: N, 6.19; Cl, 14.87. $C_{13}H_{13}ON$, HCl requires N, 5.94; Cl, 15.07 per cent.). The compound when heated to its melting point gave hydrochloric acid fumes. The hydrochloride or the free base itself does not give any sharp coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

Methylacetylacetoneamine and Cyanoacetamide: Formation of 3-Cyano-4:5:6-trimethyl-2-pyridone.—Methylacetylacetoneamine was

prepared by shaking with liquor ammonia (*cf.* Combes and Combes, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1893, *iii*, 7, 778) and crystallised from a mixture of chloroform and petroleum ether, m.p. 112°. (Found: N, 12.53. $C_6H_{11}ON$ requires N, 12.39 per cent.). Its alcoholic solution with ferric chloride gives no appreciable colour. The condensation with cyanoacetamide was brought about in the usual way. The crystals obtained, melted at 306° after crystallisation from alcohol and was found to be identical with the compound 3-cyano-4:5:6-trimethyl-2-pyridone previously obtained from methylacetylacetone and cyanoacetamide in presence of piperidine (Basu, *loc. cit.*). But when the amine was heated with benzalbenzoylacetone in an oil-bath at 120-25° for about 8 hours no definite condensation product was isolated.

Benzalbenzoylacetone and p-Toluoylacetoneamine: Formation of 2-Methyl-4:6-diphenyl-3-p-toluoyl-5-acetyl-1:4-dihydropyridine (XIII).—Benzalbenzoylacetone was prepared according to Knoevenagel and Erler (*Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 2131) and obtained in shining crystals, m.p. 99°, from petroleum ether. This (3 g.) was heated with *p*-toluoylacetoneamine (2.1 g.) on an oil-bath at 120° for 5 hours. The reaction mixture was treated with a few c.c. of alcohol when a yellow crystalline product (about 2.2 g.) separated out. This on crystallisation from alcohol (charcoal) melted at 183°. (Found: C, 82.09; H, 6.55; N, 3.31. $C_{28}H_{25}O_2N$ requires C, 82.55; H, 6.14; N, 3.44 per cent.). It is easily soluble in warm chloroform, benzene and acetic acid but insoluble in petroleum ether. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with an intense red coloration but is precipitated unchanged on dilution with water.

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